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**INFO 110A “AI: Foundations & Society”
University of Washington Information School
Spring, 2026, Syllabus (VERSION: 3/28/2026)**

Catalog Description: Introduces the fundamentals of AI, including the basics of historic and modern AI systems. Students will develop fluency with AI systems, from models and datasets to responsible usage, and will learn how to use and evaluate these systems using widely accessible tools. No programming required.

Introduction: AI is everywhere: on the news, in job descriptions, at family dinners. The term is ubiquitous. And yet, it is difficult to know where to begin. Things change fast, and so too do our expectations of what we should know, and how we utilize this knowledge. This course is intended to address precisely this challenge. Throughout the quarter, we will cover basics ranging from definitions to the central components of modern AI systems: models, data, tasks, and applications. Through course lectures, activities, assignments, and conversations with expert AI researchers and practitioners across a range of application areas, students will also develop exposure to not only large language models, foundation models, generative AI, and emerging AI methods but also other facets of AI: AI ethics, ML operations, data centers, and interdisciplinary approaches. By the end of the course, students should be able to actively participate in discussions surrounding AI.

Prerequisites: **None!** This course is open to all undergraduates with an interest in learning more about AI and a willingness to explore an interdisciplinary approach. No coding background is necessary, and there are no expectations of prior knowledge of AI.

Learning Goals:

1. Students will be able to holistically assess AI systems and determine when and how to adopt them.
2. Students will learn how to develop their own AI values, as well as ethically and responsibly use AI systems.
3. Students will be able to actively participate in discussions surrounding AI in future professional contexts.
4. Students will develop an understanding of the history of AI and how it relates to people, from those represented in datasets to those training and using the AI models.

Meeting Time: Tuesdays & Thursdays, 10:30 AM -12:20 PM

Location: Mary Gates Hall (MGH) 389

Assessment: This course will be graded on the 4.0 system.

Office Hours: after class on Tuesdays, 12:30-1:30 (we will walk to my office, MGH 330T)

Accessibility & Accommodations: Please do not hesitate to reach out to me (bcgl@uw.edu) regarding accommodations (disability, religious, family, etc.). Here are links to university policies regarding [disability accommodations](#) and [religious accommodations](#), and feel free to contact me. Moreover, here is the Information School's [list of student resources](#), which details disability accommodations, physical & mental health, legal resources, study centers & writing centers, financial aid, and community connections.

Inclusivity Statement: As part of the Information School, this course foregrounds a commitment to an inclusive learning environment – one that prioritizes mutual respect, the thoughtful exchange of ideas, and the growing of community, both within and beyond the classroom (whether in-person or virtual). Throughout the quarter, I ask that all of us find meaning in cultivating this environment through listening, active learning, and respectful disagreement. In difficult conversations, we will promote the values of the Information School, as highlighted within IDEAS and within the Informatics program. I also ask that we all bring intentionality in reflecting on our positionality as it relates to this course, including the readings, interviews, and conversations we embark on together. If you ever feel as though any of the values in this inclusivity statement are not being foregrounded, please feel free to reach out to me. I will make every effort to incorporate your feedback, and I am grateful to have the opportunity to share this quarter with you.

Late Policy: For assignments, you will receive a 5% penalty on your final grade for every day beyond the submission deadline, unless you speak with me before the deadline. Please communicate with me, as we should be able to make a plan for late submission together – with a lower penalty if you do so.

AI Policy: Given that this is a course on AI fundamentals, and that we will be using AI systems throughout the quarter, you are allowed to utilize AI throughout the assignments (including the final project) but **not the discussion posts**. For the assignments, this covers research, writing, and coding (if utilized in your final project). However, you **must include screenshots and transcripts of how you have used AI in your assignment, along with a description of how you believe AI has influenced the formulation of your ideas, writing, and deliverables**. The only exception is in the in-class portion of Assignment 2, which will be conducted without the use of any AI tools.

Questions: If you have any questions, please don't hesitate to reach out!

Contact Information: bcgl@uw.edu

(Weekly Overview & Assignments are on the next page)

Weekly Overview

Week 1: Introduction

- **3/31: Course Introduction**
 - AI in the public imagination vs. AI in reality
 - Overview of syllabus, assignments, expectations for lectures, goals for the course
- **4/2: Basics & Definitions**
 - A *very* brief history of AI
 - Definitions: What are models? What is training? Supervised & unsupervised & semi-supervised, oh my!
 - An overview of subfields & tasks

Week 2: AI Ethics, Responsible AI: A Framework for the Quarter

- **4/7: Checklists, Best Practices, Accountability**
 - How to holistically audit AI systems
- **4/9: Policy, Ethics, Copyright & Regulation**

Week 3: Data

- **4/14: A Brief History of Datasets**
 - From IRIS to MNIST, from ImageNet to all of the internet
 - Data collection, data processing, data labeling
- **4/16: Databases, Data Centers, Data Management for AI**

Week 4: Models

- **4/21: A Brief History of AI Models**
 - From regression to feature engineering to foundation models
 - Training, pre-training, finetuning, and beyond
- **4/23: Unifying Models, Data, and Compute**
 - Scaling laws: model capacity vs. data input
 - GPUs & computing power

Week 5: Critical AI

- **4/28: AI and Its Harms**
- **4/30: AI and Its Resources**

Week 6: Generative AI

- **5/5 & 5/7: A Brief History, Applications, Open Science**
 - From rules-based computer poetry to GANs to [foundation models](#)
 - How LLMs work
 - Different foundation models:
 - Other LLMs: OLMo, LLaMa, Alpaca, Copilot

- Vision & Multimodal: GPT-5, CLIP, LLaVa, 4M, Claude, etc.

Week 7: Human-AI Interaction

- **5/12: Going Beyond AI in Isolation**
 - The human-AI team, humans in the loop
 - Design, user interfaces, and AI
- **5/14: **In-class Portion of Assignment 2****

Week 8: AI Operations & Infrastructure: Building, Deploying, and Maintaining AI Systems (aka, “How do you actually make this stuff work?”)

- **5/19: Infrastructure, Scale in Practice**
 - Servers, GPUs, engineers, researchers, cloud resources, energy, costs
 - Data volume, scaling to users, reducing latency
- **5/21: A Real-World Model, Scale in Practice**
 - Infrastructure: How a model is deployed:
 - Training, testing, deploying, maintaining, re-training
 - Development / production

Week 9: AI Futures

- **5/26: AI Futures: Speculation, Imagination**
- **5/28: Designing our Own AI Futures**

Week 10: AI Applications

- **6/2: We will vote on the most interesting applications of AI for us to discuss!**
- **6/4: *In-person project fair!***

Assignments

- Weekly reading reflections: 25%
- Assignment 1, or “Anatomy of an AI System”: 20%
- Assignment 2, or “AI Values”: 25%
- Final project (individual or in groups): 30%
- Extra credit: bringing an article to share during Tuesday classes (0.5%)

Weekly Reading Reflections (25% of final grade)

Every week, you will contribute two reading responses in total on Canvas, one in advance of each class. These responses may consist of:

- 1) contributing a reflection about the reading,
- 2) asking an engaged question about the reading, or
- 3) responding to a reflection posted by a classmate.

The goal here is to facilitate conversation in advance of our class meetings! You must post your responses **before** we discuss that reading in class so that I can use the Canvas conversations to steer our in-class discussions.

Assignment 1: Anatomy of an AI System (20%)

AI systems are everywhere. You use one every time you perform a search online, or ask Siri a question, or interact with a chatbot. The goal of this assignment is to audit **one real-world AI system of your choosing**. It can be a system that you use daily, or a system that you want to learn more about. All that is required is that you have access to the system so you can interact with it and reflect on these interactions.

Here, we will draw from the checklist/responsible operations/best practices readings from the beginning of week 2. Your submission will take the form of a completed checklist auditing the system of your choosing in a holistic manner, across various facets: the AI model, the underlying data, privacy, ethics, transparency, etc. [The checklist](#) that you will be using is modified from our readings.

Deliverable: you will upload a PDF consisting of your completed checklist. The target word count on this assignment is **2,000 words of your own writing**. You may include diagrams, screenshots, and other visuals as you see fit.

Assignment 2: AI Values Statement (25%): in class

In this assignment, you will write your own AI values statement, justify it, and apply your values to a series of case studies. The assignment will consist of two central components, which will be weighted equally in determining your grade on the assignment:

- 1) **The AI values statement itself**, consisting of values that are more important to you, along with brief justifications and examples for each. You are allowed to be as pro- or anti-AI as you would like; you will be evaluated on how you justify these values.

You may prepare your values in advance of class and may bring them to class on a single-sided page. However, you will provide justifications/examples for each value during the in-class assessment on your own.

To aid in brainstorming, here are example AI values statements:

- [Smithsonian AI Values Statement](#)
- [Washington, D.C., AI Values](#)
- [University of Washington Libraries AI Values Framework](#)

For the AI Values Statement, you will provide **6 values**, with the following considerations:

- Each value should touch on a different dimension of AI
- They should reflect your own values! (rather than writing from the perspective of an organization / company / governmental agency)
- Your statements should be in the first person: “I will...”

- They should be specific enough that they are actionable (i.e., help you determine *whether* or *how* to use an AI system)
- 1 paragraph (100-200 words) of elaboration for each value and how you will act on this value (i.e., transparency -> “I will work with AI models that are open and free to use”)

2) **Two case studies applying your AI values statement**, which will **not** be provided in advance. With these case studies, you will be asked to argue whether the situations are compatible or incompatible with your AI values, and how you would respond to the situation. Again, you will not be graded based on your view itself (it can be as pro- or anti-AI as you would like) but rather *how you argue your view in relation to the case study*.

Final Project (30%)

For the final project, you will re-imagine AI in some way. This can take many forms. You could write your own speculative fiction about a new AI system in an imagined society. You could write a zine about your AI values, communicating them to a new audience. You could prototype your own AI system or finetune your own AI model. You could interview a series of AI practitioners. You could design a new interface for interacting with a large language model. You could create your own checklist for auditing AI systems. The list goes on!

Because this assignment is open-ended, we will devote significant class time to discussing ideas collectively. In addition, I will devote class time to talking with each of you about their proposed project idea. I also encourage you to reach out with any questions you may have during the brainstorming phase so you are as well-positioned with your project as possible. I look forward to hearing your ideas, and more to come!

You will be graded on **three deliverables**:

- **The thing that you make (50%)**
- **A short paper (500-1000 words) accompanying the project that details your process and reflects on how and why you made what you made (25%)**
- **Your 5-minute presentation during the in-class fair (25%)**

You are allowed to work in groups – more information on this to follow.

Extra Credit (0.5%)

Note that each week, we will devote the first 15 minutes of each Tuesday’s class time to discussing current events in AI: **bring an article or snippet of AI news, and we will discuss it in class!** (you will receive extra credit for doing so: 0.5% added to your final grade!)